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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Ethernet for Space</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA13-404</i>
General application	<i>Space</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Andrea Coronetti, The Exploration Company</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	
Dates of the experiment	<i>17.06.2025</i>
Facility	<i>GSI SIS-18</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>13 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The goal of this proposal is to perform SEE testing of active integrated circuits that are pivotal in the development of innovative and future solutions for on-board communication in space missions. The objective of the test was to verify the SEE susceptibility of some automotive parts to heavy ions for use in space missions. The elements under test were an ethernet switch and a DDR4 memory. In particular, the aim of the test was to exclude destructive SEEs at LET of 37 MeV/(mg/cm²) for the two parts and to verify whether non-destructive SEL would be possible. SEFI and other types of SEUs were also monitored.

Experiment test report

Ethernet switch

An evaluation board available from the manufacturer of the ethernet switch was used for the purpose of the test. The evaluation board has two DUTs mounted. During the test only a single DUT was irradiated at a time. The evaluation board allows the powering of the DUTs and the connection to the ethernet ports. This ethernet switch has 10 ports. During the test 2 ethernet ports were assessed and the rest were verified to be functional after the target fluence was achieved. Since the board uses a power management device, in order to assess whether SEL may occur, 0-Ohm resistors were removed and the current flow was deviated to an SEL measurement unit which provides the current measurement and is read with a Raspberry Pi. These allowed monitoring of the 3.3 V channels. The monitoring on this channel along with the monitoring on the power supply determines when a power cycle is needed. The whole test setup is summarized in *Figure 1*.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

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Figure 1. Test setup schematic.

Concerning communication, the ethernet switch provides ethernet communication between a laptop and a second Raspberry Pi. A simple data transmission is implemented. The laptop sends a counter to the Raspberry Pi, which has to echo back the data received. Several soft SEEs can be identified in this respect:

- If there is no continuative (i.e., several iterations reaching the timeout) reception of the data, a communication SEFI is considered. An example is shown in Figure 2. This requires external power cycle to be recovered.
- If a single glitch timeout occurs and the device recovers on its own, this is considered a communication SEU or timeout SEU.
- If the data echoed back by the Raspberry Pi is corrupted or shifted, this is considered a Data SEU.

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1 [INFO]: response time: 100 ms, errors: 0, loss: 0.00 %, TX: '36', RX: 'ECHO: 36'
2 [INFO]: response time: 113 ms, errors: 0, loss: 0.00 %, TX: '37', RX: 'ECHO: 37'
3 [INFO]: response time: 162 ms, errors: 0, loss: 0.00 %, TX: '38', RX: 'ECHO: 38'
4 [INFO]: response time: 139 ms, errors: 0, loss: 0.00 %, TX: '39', RX: 'ECHO: 39'
5 [INFO]: response time: 118 ms, errors: 0, loss: 0.00 %, TX: '40', RX: 'ECHO: 40'
6 [ERROR]: response time: 2004 ms, errors: 1, loss: 2.44 %, TX: '41', RX: 'Timeout'
7 [ERROR]: response time: 2015 ms, errors: 2, loss: 4.76 %, TX: '42', RX: 'Timeout'
8 [ERROR]: response time: 2004 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.98 %, TX: '43', RX: 'Timeout'
9 [INFO]: response time: 61 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.82 %, TX: '44', RX: 'ECHO: 44'
10 [INFO]: response time: 147 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.67 %, TX: '45', RX: 'ECHO: 45'
11 [INFO]: response time: 143 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.52 %, TX: '46', RX: 'ECHO: 46'
12 [INFO]: response time: 144 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.38 %, TX: '47', RX: 'ECHO: 47'
13 [INFO]: response time: 151 ms, errors: 3, loss: 6.25 %, TX: '48', RX: 'ECHO: 48'

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Figure 2. Example of communication SEFI. A communication SEU would be just one timeout triggered.

Two DUTs were irradiated with Uranium ions. The devices were not delidded, so the package is taken into account to determine the LET at the sensitive volume. The LET during the test was then 40 MeV/(mg/cm²). The flux was kept at 1000 ions/cm²/spill and the test of one DUT was concluded when a fluence of about 10⁶ ions/cm² was reached. No destructive SEEs nor any type of SEL were observed during the test. Other types of events were observed and are summarized in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Summary of soft SEEs.

DUT	LET [MeV/(mg/cm ²)]	Total fluence [ions/cm ²]	SEFI	Timeout SEU	Data SEU
2	40	1.00 x 10 ⁶	78	12	1
1	40	8.98 x 10 ⁵	115	24	2

DDR4

The DDR4 memory was also tested by means of an evaluation board. The DDR4 works with enabled ECC. The evaluation board embeds a processor that uses the DDR4 as external RAM memory. A single DDR4 is mounted on the evaluation board. Therefore, two evaluation boards were available for the test. Both boards have been modified by removing the 0-Ohm resistors and deviate the current flow to an SEL measurement unit that is interfaced by a Raspberry Pi. This allows monitoring 1.8 V channels. SEL on voltages as low as 1.1 V has not been observed so far in the literature and was not monitored during the test. The monitoring done by the SEL measurement unit and the power supply is used to determine when an SEL occurs and if power cycle is needed. *Figure 3* shows the test setup schematic. 1.5 GB (12 Gbits) were used for the purpose of SEU and stuck bit testing. The memory is pre-written with a checkerboard pattern. During the irradiation, the processor reads the memory pattern. If corruption is found, the address where the errors occurred are flagged and information is sent to a laptop via ethernet channels. Due to strong sensitivity to SEFIs, it was however finally not possible to really perform an SEU test. Similarly, even if the device was suffering a SEFI, it was decided to continue the irradiation in steps of 10⁵ ions/cm² to assess whether destructive SEEs, SEL or stuck bits would occur.

Figure 3. Test setup schematic.

Two DUTs were irradiated with Uranium ions. The devices were not delidded, so the package is taken into account to determine the LET at the sensitive volume. Since the DUT contains two sensitive dies interleaved by a dummy die, the LETs in the two sensitive chips are not exactly the same. However, through SRIM simulations it was determined that the top chip would see an LET of 38 MeV/(mg/cm²) and the bottom chip and LET of 39 MeV/(mg/cm²). The flux was kept at 5000 ions/cm²/spill and the test of one DUT was concluded when a fluence of about 10⁵ ions/cm² was reached. The evaluation board was power cycled to verify functionality as well as presence of stuck bits in the DDR4. The same procedure was repeated 10 times per DUT until a total fluence of 10⁶ ions/cm² was reached. No destructive SEEs nor any type of SEL were observed during the test of the two DDR4. SEFI were observed, but not characterized in terms of cross sections. It was not possible to determine SEUs. Stuck bits were not observed at the end of each run and up to the observed total fluence.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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